

Performance Evaluation of Common Encryption Algorithms for Throughput and Energy Consumption of a Wireless System

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ABSTRACT

This work evaluates the effect(s) of common encryption algorithms on throughput, processing time and power consumption of a wireless system. Three different encryption algorithms commonly used for wireless local area network (WLANs) namely; Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), Data Encryption Standard (DES), and Blowfish were evaluated and studied. The three algorithms were simulated and compiled using the default settings in .NET 2010 visual studio. The results show that Blowfish algorithm outperforms other algorithms in terms of energy consumption, processing time and throughput for Text data, Audio files and Image files. While DES is optimal both in its throughput and energy requirement.

Keyword: AES, Blowfish, DES, Encryption algorithm, Visual studio, WLAN.

INTRODUCTION

The need for secure communication dates back to the beginnings of human society. Ever since the first men started to gather in small groups, there was the need to transmit some kind of information from someone to someone else, while keeping it hidden from others. In the early days of civilized man, they would make a simple pattern change to an alphabet, or substitute other letters or numbers into the written messages, to successfully hide the private information. Cryptography has accompanied us throughout history, and is still very much present today. In our modern day world, with the invention of computers, networks and the internet, we are faced with a situation where our private information is available digitally in many forms and in many more places than most of us would like. Cryptography plays a major part in every person's life more than most people realize. Encryption of our medical, financial, tax and personal information is vital to keeping our information out of the hands of those who wish to do us wrong. Although the main goal remains the same since many centuries, the way cryptography is done has significantly changed in the last decades. Encryption is the conversion of data into a form, called a ciphertext, which cannot be easily understood by unauthorized people. Decryption is the process of converting encrypted data back into its original form, so that it can be understood. The use of encryption or decryption is as old as the art of communication. In wartime, a cipher, often incorrectly called a code, can be employed to keep the enemy from obtaining the contents of transmissions. (Technically, a code is a means of representing a signal without the intent of keeping it secret). Simple ciphers include the substitution of letters for numbers, the rotation of letters in the alphabet, and the "scrambling" of voice signals by inverting the side band frequencies. Complex ciphers work according to sophisticated

computer algorithms that rearrange the data bits in digital signals.

Figure 1: Encryption-Decryption Flow

In order to easily recover the contents of an encrypted signal, the correct encryption key is required. The key is an algorithm that undoes the work of the encryption algorithm. Alternatively, a computer can be used in an attempt to break the cipher. The more complex the encryption algorithm, the more difficult it becomes to eavesdrop on the communications without access to the key. Encryption is especially important in wireless communications. This is because wireless circuits are easier to tap than the hard-wired circuits. Nevertheless, encryption is a good idea when carrying out any kind of sensitive transaction, such as a credit-card purchase online, or the discussion of a company secret between different departments in the organization. The stronger the cipher the harder it is for unauthorized people to break it. However, as the strength of encryption increases, so does the cost.

[1] described the Quality of Encryption Measurement of Bitmap Images with RC6, MRC6, and Rijndael Block Cipher Algorithms. This work showed the energy consumption of different common symmetric key encryptions on handheld devices. It is found that after only 600 encryptions of a 5 MB file using Triple-DES the remaining battery power is 45% and subsequent encryptions are not possible as the battery dies rapidly.

[2] concluded that in the "Encryption and Power Consumption in Wireless LANs-N", AES is faster and more efficient than other encryption algorithms. When the transmission of data is considered, there is insignificant difference in performance of different symmetric key schemes. Increasing the key size by 64 bits of AES leads to increase in energy consumption of about 8% without any data transfer.

In [3], "Physical layer driven protocol and algorithm design for energy-efficient wireless sensor networks," a study of security measure level has been proposed for a web programming language to analyze four Web browsers. This study considered measuring the performances of encryption process at the programming language's script with the Web browsers. This is followed by conducting tests simulation in order to obtain the best encryption algorithm versus Web browser.

Basic Terminologies

A message to be sent is called a *cleartext* or *plaintext* which will be encoded using *encryption*. The resulting encrypted message is called the *ciphertext* which is sent to the receiver. Upon receiving the ciphertext, *decryption* of the ciphertext is achieved by using a *key* and the coding method (*cryptographic algorithm*).

Cryptography is the science of keeping messages secret and it is practiced by *cryptographers*. *Cryptanalysis* is the art of breaking ciphers without the use of the proper key as practiced by *cryptanalysts*.

A method of encryption or decryption is called a *cipher*. Secrecy of the algorithms used for cryptographic methods was common in the past (such as Caesar's cipher). Most methods now do not only rely on secrecy of the algorithm, but also on the intrinsic mathematical difficulty of its cryptanalysis.

Cryptographic Algorithm

There are two classes of key-based cryptographic algorithms; symmetric (or secret key) and asymmetric (or public-key) algorithms. The main difference in these classes of algorithms is that while the same key is used for both encryption and decryption for symmetric algorithms, different keys are used in asymmetric algorithms for encryption and decryption and the decryption key cannot be efficiently derived from the encryption key. Symmetric algorithms can be divided into two types, stream ciphers and block ciphers. A stream cipher can encrypt a single byte of plaintext at a time, whereas block ciphers operate on a specific number of bits (usually 64 bits) and encrypt them as a single unit. Asymmetric algorithms allow the encryption key to be made public, allowing anyone to encrypt messages with that key. However, only the proper recipient can decrypt the message. The encryption key is called the public key and the decryption key is known as the private key (or secret key).

Cryptography can also be classified according to the type of operation used for transforming plaintext to cipher text. All encryption algorithms are based on two general principles: *Substitution*, in which each element in the plaintext (bit, letter, group of bits or letters) is mapped into another element and *Transposition* in which elements in the plaintext are rearranged.

Encryption Algorithms

There are several different algorithms which have been proposed over the years. Some of these algorithms that are used in the SSL, SSH and IP security protocols are discussed below.

Data Encryption Standard (DES)

In the early 1970's IBM developed the Data Encryption Standard (DES) cipher. The algorithm, a block cipher, works by encrypting data in 64 bit blocks. The decryption of the ciphertext uses the same algorithm with differences in the key schedule. The length of the key is 56 bits. DES operates on a 64-bit block of plaintext and after the first permutation; the block is broken to two halves of 32 bits (left and right). Sixteen rounds of identical operations are performed using a function $f(t)$ in which the data is combined with the key. After the sixteenth round, the two halves are rejoined and the inverse permutation of the first permutation is taken to finish the algorithm.

The function takes the key bits and shifts them and then 48 of the 56 bits are selected. The right half of the data is expanded to 48 bits through an expansion permutation and it is exclusive-ORed with the 48 bit key. This result is put through a substitution algorithm and permuted again. The output of the Function f combined with the left half with an exclusive-OR. The result becomes the new left half and the old left half becomes the right half and the operation is repeated another 15 times (16 times in total). DES has been cracked in less than twenty four hours using a simple brute force attacks. For this reason DES is considered to be an out-dated and easily hacked encryption option. The decryption algorithm is the same as the encryption algorithm except that the keys are used in reverse order. That is, if the encryption keys for each round are $k_1, k_2, k_3, \dots, k_{16}$, then the decryption keys will be the reverse order: $k_{16}, k_{15}, k_{14}, \dots, k_1$.

Figure 2: The structure of DES

Figure 3: Action of DES

Triple Data Encryption Standard (3DES)

As an improvement on Data Encryption Standard (DES), in the late 1970's IBM developed the Triple Data Encryption Standard (3DES). The Triple Data Encryption Algorithm (3DES) is

simply the DES used three times in succession. It is this successive use which makes 3DES much harder to crack than DES. 3DES solves the problem of the too-short 56 bit key length used in DES by utilizing a key length of 168 bits (three separate 64 bit keys are used to process the same bit of unencrypted text). 3DES is still being widely used in financial transactions today and is seen as being fairly secure.

Rivest Cipher Family (RC2 and RC4)

In the late 1980's the "Rivest Cipher" or RC2 encryption algorithm was developed. Developed by Ron Rivest, the RC2 block cipher algorithm uses a 64bit block size and variable key length. RC2 uses a source-heavy Feistel network with 16 rounds of mixing and 2 rounds of mashing. RC2 was originally created for use by Lotus in their Lotus Notes messaging software. As an early cipher it was good for its time and remained a secret for a few years before it became publicly available via the internet. RC2 is vulnerable to attack using 234 chosen plaintexts. RC2 is seen as a fairly easily cracked cipher and not an optimal solution for today's encryption needs. After the invention of RC2, Ron Rivest improved on it with the creation of RC4. RC4 is a software stream cipher and currently the standard encryption used in SSL and WEP wireless applications today. For these applications it is considered "secure enough" however, RC4 is vulnerable to crack because it is known to not be as "random" as necessary for encryption. RC4 is better than its predecessor RC2 but is not recommended for use in new applications today which require higher levels of security.

Blowfish

Blowfish is a keyed, symmetric block cipher, designed in 1993 by Bruce Schneier and included in a large number of cipher suites and encryption products. Blowfish provides a good encryption rate in software and no effective cryptanalysis of it has been found to date. However, the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) now receives more attention. Schneier designed Blowfish as a general-purpose algorithm, intended as an alternative to the ageing DES and free of the problems and constraints associated with other algorithms. The algorithm is placed in the public domain, and can be freely used by anyone. Blowfish has a 64-bit block size and a variable key length from 1 bit up to 448 bits. It is a 16-round Feistel cipher and uses large key-dependent S-boxes. In structure it resembles CAST-128, which uses fixed S-boxes.

The diagram in Fig 4 shows the action of Blowfish. Each line represents 32 bits. The algorithm keeps two subkey arrays: the 18-entry P-array and four 256-entry S-boxes. The S-boxes accept 8-bit input and produce 32-bit output. One entry of the P-array is used every round, and after the final round, each half of the data block is XORed with one of the two remaining unused P-entries.

Figure 4 and 5 below shows Blowfish's F-function. The function splits the 32-bit input into four eight-bit quarters, and uses the quarters as input to the S-boxes. The outputs are added modulo 2^{32} and XORed to produce the final 32-bit output. Decryption is exactly the same as encryption, except that P_1, P_2, \dots, P_{18} are used in the reverse order.

Figure 4: Blowfish's F-function

Figure 5: Action of Blowfish

International Data Encryption Algorithm (IDEA)

The International Data Encryption Algorithm (IDEA) is believed to be a strong and secure block algorithm. It operates on a 64 bit plaintext blocks with a key of size 128 bits. The same algorithm is used for encryption as well as decryption. The design philosophy behind this algorithm is to mix operations from different algebraic groups. The algebraic groups that IDEA uses are: XOR, addition modulo 2^{16} (addition, ignoring overflow), and multiplication modulo 2^{16} (multiplication, ignoring overflow). These operations are easily implemented in both hardware and software and they operate on 16-bit sub-blocks which makes it efficient on 16-bit processors as well. The 64 bit block is subdivided into 4 16 bit sub-blocks (X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4). The first round of eight rounds takes these sub-blocks and XORed, added and multiplied with one another and with six 16-bit sub-blocks of key material. Between each round, the second and third sub-blocks are swapped. And the results are reattached to produce the ciphertext.

There are 52 (six for each round and four for the final transformation) key sub-blocks. The 128 bit key is divided into eight 16 bit sub-keys. The first six sub-keys are used for the

first round and the remaining two are used for the first two sub-keys. Decryption is exactly the same as the encryption process except that the key sub-blocks are reversed and slightly different. The key sub-blocks are either additive or multiplicative inverses of the encryption key sub-blocks (the multiplicative inverse of 0 is 0 for IDEA). The algorithm can work in any block cipher mode discussed above.

Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)

Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is a specification for the encryption of electronic data and it supersedes DES. It is available in many different encryption packages. AES is the first publicly accessible and open cipher approved by the National Security Agency (NSA) for top secret information. Originally called Rijndael, the cipher was developed by two Belgian cryptographers, Joan Daemen and Vincent Rijmen, and submitted by them to the AES selection process. The name *Rijndael* was derived from the names of the two inventors.

AES performs well on a wide variety of hardware, from 8-bit smartcards to high-performance computers. It is based on a design principle known as a Substitution permutation network. It is fast in both software and hardware. Unlike its predecessor, DES, AES does not use a Feistel network. AES has a fixed block size of 128 bits and a key size of 128, 192, or 256 bits, whereas Rijndael can be specified with block and key sizes in any multiple of 32 bits, with a minimum of 128 bits. The block size has a maximum of 256 bits, but the key size has no theoretical maximum.

The AES cipher is specified as a number of repetitions of transformation rounds that convert the input plaintext into the final output of ciphertext. Each round consists of several processing steps, including one that depends on the encryption key. A set of reverse rounds are applied to transform ciphertext back into the original plaintext using the same encryption key.

Table 1: Comparison Table of Popular Symmetric Key Encryption Algorithms

Algorithm	Created by	Key size	Block Size	Algorithm Structure	Rounds	Cracked	Existing cracks
Rijndael (AES)	Joan Daemen & Vincent Rijmen in 1998	128 bits, 192 bits, 256bits	128 Bits	Substitution Permutation Network	10, 12 or 14	No	Side channel attacks
Twofish	Bruce Schneier in 1993	128 bits, 192 bits or 256 bits	128 bits	Feistel Network	16	No	Truncated differential cryptanalysis
Blowfish	Bruce Schneier in 1993	32-448 bits in steps of 8bits. 128 bits by default	64 bits	Feistel Network	16	No	Truncated differential cryptanalysis
RC4	Ron Rivest in 1987	Variable	Variable Stream	Unknown		Yes	Distinguishers based on weak key schedule
RC2	Ron Rivest in 1987	8-128 bits in steps of 8bits. 64 bits by default	64 bits Source	Heavy Feistel Network-	16 Mixing 2Mashing	Yes	Related-Key attack
TripleDES	IBM in 1978	112 bits or 168 bits	64 bits	Feistel Network	48	No	Theoretically possible
DES	IBM in 1975	56 bits	64 bits	Feistel Network	16	Yes	Brute force attack, differential cryptanalysis, linear cryptanalysis, Davies' attack

Experimental Design

System Parameters

The experiments are conducted using Intel Celeron 64bit 2.20GHz CPU processor with 3GB of RAM. The simulation program is compiled using the default settings in .NET 2010

visual studio for windows applications. Some of the tools used in the programs are buttons and a blank windows form. The operating system installed on the laptop is Windows7 home premium. In the experiments, the first laptop encrypts a different file size for text data (.doc files), audio files

(.mp3 files) and image files (.jpg files). Three encryption algorithms that are selected in the experiment are AES (key size: 256 bits), DES (key size: 64 bits), and Blowfish (key size: 256 bits) as shown below.

Figure 6: Build up of the .NET environment (User Interface) in Microsoft Visual Studio 2010 for AES.

Figure 7: Build up of the .NET environment (User Interface) in Microsoft Visual Studio 2010 for DES and Blowfish.

These implementations are thoroughly tested and are optimized to give the maximum performance for each algorithm. In this work, the algorithms were implemented, and their performance was compared by encrypting input files of varying types, contents and sizes. The algorithms were implemented in a uniform language (Visual Basic), using their standard specifications. Microsoft Visual Studio 2010 using VB.NET environment was used in the compiling of the algorithm of AES. The results are checked and tested by a different implementation programs to give the maximum performance for the algorithms and make sure the results are the same on any platform. The three performance metrics measured are: Encryption time, throughput and battery power consumed.

Encryption time - This is the time that an encryption algorithm takes to produce a cipher text from a plaintext. Encryption time is used to calculate the throughput of an encryption scheme.

Note that encryption time is estimated in seconds via stop watch.

Throughput - The throughput of the encryption scheme is the total plaintext in bytes encrypted divided by the encryption time. It is a measure of the data-transfer rate through a complex communications or networking scheme. Throughput is considered an indication of the overall performance of the system. For example, the throughput of a server depends on the processor type, operating system in

use, hard disk capacity. The throughput of the encryption scheme is calculated as in the equation below:

$$\text{Throughput of encryption} = \frac{T_p \text{ (bytes)}}{E_t \text{ (seconds)}}$$

Where:

T_p - Total plain text (bytes)

E_t - Encryption time (second)

Battery power consumed - The *CPU clock cycles* are a metric, reflecting the energy consumption of the CPU while operating on encryption operations. Each cycle of CPU will consume a small amount of energy. For computation of the energy cost of encryption, by using the cycles, the operating voltage of the CPU, and the average current drawn for each cycle, we can calculate the energy consumption of cryptographic functions.

We present a basic energy cost of encryption represented by the product of the total number of clock cycles taken by the encryption and the average current drawn by each CPU clock cycle. The basic encryption cost is in unit of ampere-cycle. To calculate the total energy cost, we divide the ampere-cycles by the clock frequency in cycles/second of a processor; we obtain the energy cost of encryption in ampere-seconds. Then, we multiply the ampere-seconds with the processor's operating voltage, and we obtain the energy cost in Joule.

For example, on average, each cycle consumes approximately 270mA on an Intel Celeron processor. For a sample calculation, with a 700 MHz CPU operating at 1.35 Volt, an encryption with 20,000 cycles would consume 7.7 μ Joule.

So, the amount of energy consumed by program P to achieve its goal (encryption or decryption) is given by

$$E = V_{cc} * I * N * \tau$$

For a given hardware, both V_{cc} and τ are fixed, $E \propto I \times N$. However, at the application level, it is more meaningful to talk about T than N, and therefore, we express energy as $E \propto I \times T$.

We replace total no of clock cycle divided by clock frequency to be duration time for encryption or decryption. Then, the amount of energy consumed by program P to achieve its goal (encryption) is given by:

$$\therefore E_{cost} = V_{cc} \times I \times T \text{ Joules}$$

Where:

V_{cc} - the supply voltage of the system

I - the average current in amperes drawn from the power source

N - the number of clock cycles. τT - the clock period.

T - N /processor's speed (seconds)

However it should be noted that the required supply voltage for the laptop used for this experiment is 5 V, while the average current drawn is 250mA. It should also be recalled that the processor's speed is 2 GHz (cycle per seconds).

- Results Comparison

A comparison is conducted between the results of selected different encryption algorithms using different setting such as different data sizes. The platforms for comparison are stated below:

- ❖ Average throughputs for the encryption process of the three algorithms under observation are compared to evaluate performance of algorithm.
- ❖ Energy consumption during each encryption process is calculated and compared to evaluate the performance of encryption algorithms.
- ❖ The Effect of Cryptographic Algorithms on Text Files Encryption time is used to calculate the throughput of an encryption scheme. In this section, Encryption throughput (Kilobytes/Sec) and energy consumption are calculated for encrypting text files (.doc files) without transmission to show which encryption is more powerful than others.

Encryption Throughput

Throughput of each encryption algorithm to encrypt different text data (Megabytes/Sec) is shown in table 2 while figure 13 is the graphical representation:

Table 2: Throughput comparison of text file encryption with AES, DES and Blowfish

Input Size (bytes)	AES	BLOWFISH	DES
381,000	6	3	3
3,259,000	15	15	15
6,183,000	25	19	20
Average Throughput (Kilobyte/Sec)	176.03	248.86	217.80

Figure 8: Average throughput of each encryption algorithm to encrypt different text data (Megabytes/Sec)

Energy Consumption

The energy consumption for encryption process for text data (.doc files) with a different data block size are shown below: For AES, using the 6,183,000 bytes file, the time is 25 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5\text{ V} \times 250\text{ mA} \times 25\text{ seconds} = 31.25\text{ joules}$

For Blowfish, using the 6,183,000 bytes file, the time is 19 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5\text{ V} \times 250\text{mA} \times 19\text{ seconds} = 23.75\text{ joules}$

For DES, using the 6,183,000 bytes file, the time is 20 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5\text{ V} \times 250\text{mA} \times 20\text{ seconds} = 25\text{ joules}$

Figure 14: Power consumption for encrypting different text document files

Results Analysis for Text Data

The results show the superiority of Blowfish algorithm over other algorithms in terms of the energy consumption (i.e. low energy consumption), processing time (i.e. low processing time), and throughput (i.e. higher throughput) in case of encryption.

When the same data is encrypted by using Blowfish and AES, it is found that Blowfish requires approximately 74 percent of the energy which is consumed for AES. It is also 71 percent faster than AES.

The Effect of Cryptographic Algorithms on Audio Files

Here, a comparison between encryption throughput and energy consumption of another type of data (audio file) will be made to check which one can perform better than others.

Encryption Throughput

A comparison between another type of data (audio file) will be made to check which one can perform better than others. Experimental results for audio data type (.mp3 files) are shown in table 3 and figure 15 below.

Table 3: Average throughput comparison of audio file encryption with AES, DES and Blowfish

Input Size (bytes)	AES	BLOWFISH	DES
856,000	8	5	6
2,418,000	14	8	10
5,065,000	20	13	15
Average Throughput (kilobyte/sec)	177.65	287.69	240.71

Figure 10: Average throughput of each encryption algorithm (Kilobytes/Sec)

Power Consumption

For AES, using the 5,065,000 bytes file, the time is 20 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5V \times 250 \text{ mA} \times 20 \text{ seconds} = 25 \text{ joules}$

For Blowfish, using the 5,065,000 bytes file, the time is 13 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5V \times 250\text{mA} \times 13 \text{ seconds} = 16.25 \text{ joules}$

For DES, using the 5,065,000 bytes file, the time is 15 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5V \times 250\text{mA} \times 15 \text{ seconds} = 18.75 \text{ joules}$

Figure 11: Power consumption for encrypting different audio Files

Results Analysis for Audio files

The results show the superiority of Blowfish algorithm over other algorithms in terms of the energy consumption, processing time, and throughput in case of encryption.

When the same data is encrypted by using Blowfish and AES, it is found that Blowfish requires approximately 65 percent of the energy which is consumed for AES. It is also 60 percent faster than AES. It should be noted that DES is also optimal in both its throughput and energy requirement here too.

The Effect of Cryptographic Algorithms on Image Files

Here, a comparison between encryption throughput and energy consumption of another type of data (image file) will be made to check which one can perform better than others in this case. Experimental results for image data type (JPG images) are shown below:

Encryption Throughput

Table 4: Throughput comparison of text file encryption with AES, DES and Blowfish

Input Size (bytes)	AES	BLOWFISH	DES
22,000	3	2	2
101,000	4	2	2
174,000	5	3	5
Average Throughput (KiloByte/Sec)	22.46	49.5	39.83

Figure 12: Average throughput of each encryption algorithm (Kilobytes/Sec) for image files

Power Consumption

For AES, using the 174,000 bytes file, the time is 5 seconds. Therefore total energy consumption is: $5V \times 250 \text{ mA} \times 5 \text{ seconds} = 6.25 \text{ joules}$

For Blowfish, using the 174,000 bytes file, the time is 13 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5V \times 250 \text{ mA} \times 3 \text{ seconds} = 3.75 \text{ joules}$

For DES, using the 174,000 bytes file, the time is 15 seconds.

Therefore total energy consumption is: $5V \times 250\text{mA} \times 5 \text{ seconds} = 6.25 \text{ joules}$

Fig 13: Power consumption for encrypting different images files

Results Analysis for Image files

From the results above, it can be observe that Blowfish again has advantage over the other two algorithms in both cases (it has higher throughput and it consumes less energy). It can also be seen that AES and DES have about the same value. This may be because the file sizes considered for images are lesser than those used in text and audio files.

General Graphical View of Throughput and Energy Consumption

Fig 14: Joint analysis of average throughput on the three algorithms on text, audio and image files

Fig 15: Joint analysis of energy consumption on text, audio and image files

CONCLUSION

This paper presents a performance evaluation of three selected symmetric encryption algorithms on throughput and energy consumption for wireless devices. The selected algorithms are AES, DES, and Blowfish. Several points were made from the experimental results. In the case of changing the data size, it was concluded that Blowfish has better performance than other two encryption algorithms used, then followed by DES. For audio files, it is found that the result is the same as in text and image documents. For image files, it was found that Blowfish has a very low energy consumption compare to the other two algorithms while AES and DES have about the same value. This could be attributed to the sizes of data involved in the image encryption process. In general, Blowfish performance was better than AES and DES performance.

Recommendation

AES can be recommended to organization that can compromise speed and energy consumption for a much secured network environment. DES is appropriate for organization who wants optimal work rate from the cryptology process. Blowfish will work better for organizations where file security is of less priority to power consumption and speed of file transfer is of utmost importance. For the future work, this research work should involve transmission of encrypted file via various types of network authentication.

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